

Safety-Eye: On Road Safety for Self-driving Vehicles using Reinforcement Learning

Avani Dave¹, Krunal Dave²

¹daveavani@gmail.com; ²krunaldave10@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

With technological advancements automotive industry is witnessing new era of transition to self-driving vehicle for everything. Self-driving cars for personal and commercial use are right across the corner to become full reality. Along with self-driving drone and robots for delivery of food and merchandise have become reality. With these advancements the safety and security of the self-driving vehicles have emerged as major concern for current times. To this end, this work proposes SafeEye a reinforcement learning based policy aware and optimized approach with federated learning to provide self-driving vehicles better and safer route map and runtime optimization. The simulation results of SafeEye based system with multiple scenarios shows promising results and opens a new research direction to explore to provide safe and informed route prediction for self-driving vehicles of next generation.

Keywords: Automotive chiplet architecture, next-generation vehicular systems, Autonomous driving, fusion sensors, ADAS, Infotainment, gem5, chiplet, Mcpat

INTRODUCTION

Self-driving vehicles have emerged as a revolutionary technology, and it has transformed the modern-day transportation landscape. Modern-day automotives have a large network of computing, sensing, and processing engines. These systems are connected to the internal and external network for exchanging boot time and runtime critical information which are used for making informed decisions at different stages. These devices have built in Global Positioning Systems (GPS), satellite networks or a connected smart application (central controller / tablet screen / phones) to help users navigate the direction from point A to point B. There has been significant research and development to aid in autonomous driving and route planning in recent years [1-6].

Self-driving cars can potentially reduce traffic accidents caused by human errors [7] and provide more safer roads to users including pedestrians [8]. The routes used by self-driving vehicles will be based on shortest distance, toll, freeway, time of the day, traffic etc. Some of the latest applications uses machine learning and AI algorithms to get runtime updates such as accidents, road work and traffic slow alerts. However, routing applications lacks in accounting for safety, user preference and current surrounding metrics such as safety (break-ins [9], vandalism [10], porch-pirates [11] etc.), pollution, ease of parking, emergency situations [12], food choices, etc. Given a city and surrounding areas have "better" and "worse" regions and local humans will be aware of the neighborhood and dynamic conditions but the self-driving vehicles (cars, robots, delivery drones etc.) currently lack in such dynamic route optimization. To this end, this work presents a novel federated learning combined with deep reinforcement learning based approach to help better route planning with dynamic changes in metrics. This work also presents promising simulation results with optimized algorithm.

It will result in adding the weights and bias to the x and y coordinates of the geo location during runtime. The algorithm will take this weights and biasing with geo coordinates into account for cooperative policy optimization and agent will act based on not only past but current situation of the environment in which it is. The server collects the feedback of each client and use it for optimizing the training model and feeds it to client application periodically. Thus, live updates of the geolocation and surrounding conditions are given to the modified CoPo algorithm. The policies are optimized on the client agent by combining local policy updates and the feedback received from the server as global policy updates.

The localized policy optimization is performed using Eq1

$$r_{i,t}^N = \frac{\sum_{j \in \mathcal{N}_{d_n}(i,t)} r_{j,t}}{|\mathcal{N}_{d_n}(i,t)|}, \text{ wherein } \mathcal{N}_{d_n}(i,t) = \{j : \|\text{Pos}(i) - \text{Pos}(j)\| \leq d_n\}. \quad (1)$$

Where, $\mathcal{N}_{d_n}(i,t)$ defines the neighbourhood of agent i for the given radius d_n at step t . The key reason for adding the global policy is to make route prediction accuracy high. As the vehicles are running in the road with dynamic surrounding and conditions of the neighbouring vehicles will also affect the reward given to the agent. When a consensus based global policy weights and biases were added to the routing algorithm. It improved the performance significantly. The co-ordinated and weighted rewards are defined using following equation:

$$r_{i,t}^C = \cos(\phi)r_{i,t} + \sin(\phi)r_{i,t}^N. \quad (2)$$

SafeEye approach for adding weights and Biases

Implementation of routing methods based on a weighted graph approach, whereby each path between two defined locations consists of a set of weighted edges (corresponding to road segments). The weights of the edges are determined by factors such as distance, speed, road aspects, pollution, weather, and safety metrics. A UI interface with sliders for different aspects can be used to control the settings for the routing method to suggest routes based on user preferences (e.g., speed and safety, avoiding construction zones, etc.)

Creation of an online database to dynamically update the edge weights in a defined area as referenced by location (lat, lon) and the time of day and routing algorithms for two end points based on the weights from previous step. This database can utilize data from public sources and optionally from sensors placed on fleet vehicles, which regularly drive through the defined area.

Creation of a hardware module for the sensors to be mounted on fleet vehicles, including speed and camera sensors, and corresponding analysis algorithms. The cameras can analyze scenery and record e.g., instances of lane closures and construction presence and mark these aspects by uploading the information to the online database service.

Evaluation

The simulation was performed by modifying the CoPo simulator and including the weights and biases from the sensors RL learning. The modified algorithm and simulation were tested on following four scenarios for success rate and accuracy.

Table 1: Depicts the success rate of different techniques compared to SafeEye

Technique	Potholes	Intersection	Lane closures	accidents
IPO	64.67	60.47	72.43	83.5
MFPO	66	69.43	67.43	81
CoPo	72.6	78.34	74.21	75.6
SafeEye	75.3	83.23	80.54	79.32

Scenario 1: when Potholes and not favourable weather conditions were feed to the simulation motel with modified CoPo. The generated weight and biases were used for making policy-based prediction and optimized route selection the accuracy of the SafeEye was increased by 3% compared to that of CoPo.

Scenario 2: Depicts when self-driving vehicle is on the road in the intersection with ongoing traffic with signal lights offs and the request for new route prediction comes to the client. The accuracy of this route and policy-based prediction with SafeEye reaches 83.23 % correct results.

Scenario 3 and Scenario 4 depicts road conditions blocked by accident and or construction on the road and lane closure as a result. In both the cases from the simulation results SafeEye outperforms the other state-of-the-art techniques and provides better route and policy-based selection coordinated route prediction.

Figure 3: Simple Directional map

Figure 4: Map with nodes and edges

Figure 5: SafeEye route map with safety weight/bias.

Figure 3 depicts the map plugin based on shortest distance between two endpoints. Figure 4 represents the Map with additional layer of CoPo based optimization for the route. Figure 5 shows the SafeEye provided route options based on safety weights and biases. The red colour road indicates the scratchy area and recommends the self-driving vehicle to potentially avoid it by choosing alternate green path.

Challenges, considerations and future improvements

SafeEye simulation results shows promising optimized route selection and recommendation with confined environment. However, it assumes that the biases and rewards are correctly awarded to the RL based agent so that feedback loop can help modified CoPo algorithm to aid in better route selection. Furthermore, the server databased can be enhanced to combine multiple sources of information such as police records, area safety updates, public events announcements etc.

CONCLUSIONS

With the increased commercialization of self-driving cars, robots, and drone the secure and safe route selection and dynamic decision making based on the current surrounding conditions becomes vital. Previous works have demonstrated use of reinforcement learning to tackle some of these issues. However, they lack in dynamic cooperated policy optimization to handle real world scenarios such as pothole, crime activity, roadblocks, constructions, weather impacts etc. Safe Eye provides the dynamic cooperated policy-based decision optimization along with usage of federated learning enabled it to proliferate the learning to the could server network and with applied weights and biases this federated learning-based approach optimizes the training model to handle such situations in the future better. The simulation results shows that SafeEye based route maps is successfully able to avoid the scratchy neighborhood during the specific time of the day and alerted the user to chose alternate route.

REFERENCES

- [1]. E. Yurtsever, J. Lambert, A. Carballo, and K. Takeda, "A survey of autonomous driving: common practices and emerging technologies," arXiv preprint arXiv:1906.05113, 2019.
- [2]. V. Talpaert, I. Sobh, B. R. Kiran, P. Mannion, S. Yogamani, A. ElSallab, and P. Perez, "Exploring applications of deep reinforcement learning for real-world autonomous driving systems," arXiv preprint arXiv:1901.01536, 2019.
- [3]. B. R. Kiran, I. Sobh, V. Talpaert, P. Mannion, A. A. A. Sallab, S. Yogamani, and P. Perez, "Deep reinforcement learning for autonomous driving: A survey," arXiv preprint arXiv:2002.00444, 2020
- [4]. W. Schwarting, J. Alonso-Mora, and D. Rus, "Planning and decisionmaking for autonomous vehicles," Annual Review of Control, Robotics, and Autonomous Systems, 2018.
- [5]. D. Gonzalez, J. P'erez, V. Milan'es, and F. Nashashibi, "A review of motion planning techniques for automated vehicles," IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems, vol. 17, no. 4, pp. 1135–1145, 2015.

- [6]. B. Paden, M. Ċ ap, S. Z. Yong, D. Yershov, and E. Frazzoli, "A ´ survey of motion planning and control techniques for self-driving urban vehicles," IEEE Transactions on intelligent vehicles, vol. 1, no. 1, pp. 33–55, 2016.
- [7]. F. Ye, S. Zhang, P. Wang and C. -Y. Chan, "A Survey of Deep Reinforcement Learning Algorithms for Motion Planning and Control of Autonomous Vehicles," 2021 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), Nagoya, Japan, 2021, pp. 1073-1080, doi: 10.1109/IV48863.2021.9575880.
- [8]. Shubbak, M. (2013, January 1). Self-Driving Cars: Legal, Social, and Ethical Aspects. RELX Group (Netherlands). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.2931847>
- [9]. Rasouli, A., & Tsotsos, J K. (2018, January 1). Joint Attention in Driver-Pedestrian Interaction: from Theory to Practice. Cornell University. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arxiv.1802.02522>
- [10]. SFO crowd sets self-driving car on fire <https://www.washingtonpost.com/technology/2024/02/12/waymo-set-on-fire-san-francisco/>
- [11]. Robbing delivery robots is now a thing <https://www.autoweek.com/news/a44839987/delivery-robots-being-robbed/>
- [12]. Porch pirates <https://www.ktalnews.com/news/consumer-reports/how-ai-and-drones-will-help-prevent-porch-pirates-after-packages-arrive/>
- [13]. self-driving car blocked ambulance <https://ktla.com/news/california/company-refutes-claim-that-self-driving-cars-blocked-california-ambulance-led-to-victims-death/#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20San%20Francisco,crews%20from%20reaching%20the%20hospital.>
- [14]. Jakob N Foerster, Yannis M Assael, Nando De Freitas, and Shimon Whiteson. Learning to communicate with deep multi-agent reinforcement learning. arXiv preprint arXiv:1605.06676, 2016.
- [15]. Simon Vanneste, Astrid Vanneste, Siegfried Mercelis, and Peter Hellinckx. Learning to communicate using counterfactual reasoning. arXiv preprint arXiv:2006.07200, 2020.
- [16]. Yali Du, Lei Han, Meng Fang, Ji Liu, Tianhong Dai, and Dacheng Tao. Liir: Learning individual intrinsic reward in multi-agent reinforcement learning. Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems, 32:4403–4414, 2019.
- [17]. Jakob Foerster, Gregory Farquhar, Triantafyllos Afouras, Nantas Nardelli, and Shimon Whiteson. Counterfactual multi-agent policy gradients. In Proceedings of the AAAI Conference on Artificial Intelligence, volume 32, 2018.
- [18]. Tabish Rashid, Mikayel Samvelyan, Christian Schroeder, Gregory Farquhar, Jakob Foerster, and Shimon Whiteson. Qmix: Monotonic value function factorisation for deep multi-agent reinforcement learning. In International Conference on Machine Learning, pages 4295–4304. PMLR, 2018.
- [19]. Oriol Vinyals, Igor Babuschkin, Wojciech M Czarnecki, Michaël Mathieu, Andrew Dudzik, Junyoung Chung, David H Choi, Richard Powell, Timo Ewalds, Petko Georgiev, et al. Grandmaster level in starcraft ii using multi-agent reinforcement learning. Nature, 575(7782):350–354, 2019.
- [20]. Johannes Heinrich and David Silver. Deep reinforcement learning from self-play in imperfect-information games. arXiv preprint arXiv:1603.01121, 2016.
- [21]. Joel Z Leibo, Vinicius Zambaldi, Marc Lanctot, Janusz Marecki, and Thore Graepel. Multi-agent reinforcement learning in sequential social dilemmas. arXiv preprint arXiv:1702.03037, 2017.
- [22]. Ryan Lowe, Yi Wu, Aviv Tamar, Jean Harb, Pieter Abbeel, and Igor Mordatch. Multi-agent actor-critic for mixed cooperative-competitive environments. Advances in neural information processing systems, 2017.
- [23]. Wilko Schwarting, Alyssa Pierson, Javier Alonso-Mora, Sertac Karaman, and Daniela Rus. Social behavior for autonomous vehicles. Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, 116(50):24972–24978, 2019
- [24]. Behrisch, Michael, et al. "SUMO—simulation of urban mobility: an overview." Proceedings of SIMUL 2011, The Third International Conference on Advances in System Simulation. ThinkMind, 2011.
- [25]. Dosovitskiy, Alexey, et al. "CARLA: An open urban driving simulator." Conference on robot learning. PMLR, 2017.
- [26]. Tang, Zheng, et al. "Cityflow: A city-scale benchmark for multi-target multi-camera vehicle tracking and re-identification." Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition. 2019.
- [27]. Cathy Wu, Aboudy Kreidieh, Kanaad Parvate, Eugene Vinitzky, and Alexandre M Bayen. Flow: Architecture and benchmarking for reinforcement learning in traffic control. arXiv preprint arXiv:1710.05465, page 10, 2017.
- [28]. Ming Zhou, Jun Luo, Julian Villeda, Yaodong Yang, David Rusu, Jiayu Miao, Weinan Zhang, Montgomery Alban, Iman Fadarar, Zheng Chen, Aurora Chongxi Huang, Ying Wen, Kimia Hassanzadeh, Daniel Graves, Dong Chen, Zhengbang Zhu, Nhat Nguyen, Mohamed Elsayed, Kun Shao, Sanjeevan Ahilan, Baokuan Zhang, Jiannan Wu, Zhengang Fu, Kasra Rezaee, Peyman Yadmellat, Mohsen Rohani, Nicolas Perez Nieves, Yihan Ni, Seyedershad Banijamali, Alexander Cowen Rivers, Zheng Tian, Daniel Palenicek, Haitham bou Ammar, Hongbo Zhang, Wulong Liu, Jianye Hao, and Jun Wang. Smarts: Scalable multiagent reinforcement learning training school for autonomous driving, 2020.